

Digital Libraries and e-Learning

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Abstract:-

Digital libraries offer opportunities for e-Learning that are not available in their physical counterparts. Digital libraries complement other learning environments, such as those provided in distance education and courses offered online. Like e-Learning environments, they provide flexibility of time and place. Digital libraries have the potential to offer unprecedented resources to support e-Learning. This paper discusses what is e-Learning, need of e-Learning, how it can be supported by the library environment and the role of digital library in e-Learning.

Keywords: Digital Library, e-Learning, Virtual Library

Brief history of e-Learning

Use of technology in learning, in the true sense, started around the beginning of this century with the invention of films and motion pictures. During World War II, the world witnessed real use of technology in learning when U.S. Army used training films to educate their army-men and to maintain consistency in U.S. based training. Since then large scale developments have taken place at different fronts like academic, government and corporate. In the sixties, early “teaching machines” and “programmed texts” paved the way for embryonic computer-based training. Instructional films became more creative and educational film business catered to both public and private sectors.

Next era of e-Learning started when television was invented. But television did not become everyone’s teacher due to lack of interactivity with the learner. The necessity of interactivity renewed efforts in the area of computer-based training (CBT). In the seventies and eighties tremendous efforts were put in this field. The real revolution in the field of e-Learning started with the coming up of Internet. As quoted by Nobel laureate Gary S. Becker in 1992, “The Internet has begun to radically change the teaching of adults in the U.S. who want to improve their skills or further their general education.” Today’s Internet (Web) is like a universal library which is anyway easy to manage and update with worldwide accessibility. Actually Internet is the perfect E-Learning tool available to all and sundry.

E-Learning Definition:-

1. It refers to learning and other supportive resources that are available through computer. E-Learning is developed to apply information technology applications to education.
2. According to Kaplan-Leiserson (2001): The term E-Learning covers a wide set of applications and processes, such as web based learning, computer based learning and virtual classrooms. It includes the delivery of content via internet, Intranet, Extranet (LAN/WAN), audio and video tapes, Satellite broadcast, CD ROM etc.
3. The Department of Education and Skills, UK (2002): E-Learning includes “a range of activities, from the effective use of electronic resources and learning technologies in the

classroom, through to a personal learning experience enabled through individual access at home or elsewhere”.

Need for e-Learning

1. Learning is self-directed, allowing students to choose content appropriate to their differing interests, needs and skills levels.
2. Accommodates multiple learning styles using a verity of delivery methods geared to different learners, more effective to entrain learners.
3. It is designed around the learner.
4. Geographical barriers are eliminated, opening up broader education options.
5. Accessibility makes scheduling easy and allows a greater number of people to attend classes. On demand access means learning can happen precisely when needed. Travel-time is reduced or eliminated.
6. It has potentially lower costs for companies needing training and for the providers.
7. It offers faster and greater students’ interaction and collaboration.
8. It also facilitates faster and greater student/instructor contact.
9. Students can enhance computer and internet skills.
10. The curriculum draws upon hundreds of established pedagogical principles.
11. It has the attention of every major university in the world, most with their own online degrees, certificate and individual courses.

Role of Digital Libraries in E – Learning

According to Gary Marchionini (1995), libraries serve three roles in the learning process-

1. **Sharing valuable resources-** Digital library plays a vital role here by allowing several information seekers to access materials simultaneously, regardless of their physical location.
2. **Preserving and organizing artifacts and ideas-** Million books project is a live example of a digital library striving for preservation of old artifacts of intellectual importance by archiving their soft copies. The material is digitized with the help of scanning devices.
3. **Bringing people and ideas together-** Digital libraries offer diverse information resources shared by groups of learners, irrespective of physical space and time. Digital libraries bring people together with different learning missions.

The main features of a digital library are as follows:

1. Information is stored in digital form;
2. Information sources are amenable to computer access;
3. Facility for multi-user search;
4. Offers network accessibility;
5. Provides user-friendly interface;
6. Facility to browse, select, retrieve, and download on the user computer;
7. Facility to have any number of copies, if required;

8. Sometimes, rare and expensive material is available.

Digital libraries are a set of electronic resources and associated technical capabilities for creating, storing, searching and dissemination of information. Digital libraries are playing a vital role in online learning education system. Most of the digital libraries are dedicated to supporting higher education and research, and they justify their investment in digital development as a powerful means of realizing the larger institutional goals of the academic community they serve. One reason for using digital libraries in e-learning is that it can store and manage large amounts of digital content such as full text, course materials, bibliographic databases, library catalogues, image and audio clips etc. Thus it provides an environment to bring together collections, services and people in support of the full life cycle of creation, dissemination and preservation of data, information and knowledge. Another reason to use digital libraries is that using various electronic tools, learners can search text materials and images easily and quickly, which can be applied broadly across all kinds of institutions. Advanced intercommunication technology, sophisticated search engines, affordable cost and large storage of digital content are the other reasons to implement a digital library in modern education.

Other advantages of digital libraries in e-Learning are:

- Digital library allows the learner to use electronic resources from anywhere, without even knowing where it is stored geographically.
- One copy of the documents could be viewed by any number of users simultaneously.
- It can be used for increasing course delivery for a large number of clients at a particular point of time. Study materials need never go out of print, and new editions can easily be created. One can carry several titles at once on a portable reader and, over time, build a personal library.
- It would be easy for non-specialists to use due to simplicity of operation.
- Links to publisher's sites for full text journals.
- It provides and facilitates online and on demand enrolment, study and examinations.
- Search results will be delivered to an e-mail box as per the user's choice.
- Protects rare books that are rapidly deteriorating due to over use and poor storage conditions.
- It is cost-effective and cost-efficient for its ability of reuse.
- It provides faster learning, increased access, clear accountability and equal education for everybody; the web is available on the desktop.
- It provides current information and helps in research work. To cope up with the advancements in technology, production of information in multidimensional forms, it becomes essential for a person to pursue additional knowledge at all times to keep him/her up-to-date in his/her field of interest. These factors are leading to the learning. Virtual conferences, collaborative work on projects which are shared among institutions, exchange of useful material and experience among teachers provide up to date information for research.

Conclusion-

In conclusion, digital library services are an essential component of quality e-Learning system. As access to internet-based course grows, an increasing number of e-learners are dispersed around the globe, often in parts of the world where physical access to the collections of large academic and research libraries is impossible. These learners are largely dependent on the quality and usefulness of services that the digital library can offer electronically.

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